

Spectrophotometric Determination of Palladium(II) and Rhodium(III) using *N,N'*-Dipyridylthiourea as a New Sensitive and Selective Complexing Agent

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N,N'-Dipyridylthiourea (DPyT) reacts with Pd^{II} and Rh^{III} to form stable coloured complexes having λ_{\max} at 330 and 335 nm respectively. The complexes obey Beer's law over the concentration range of 0.24–2.88 $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$ for Pd and 0.60–3.56 $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$ for Rh. In the presence of moderate excess of diverse ions both Pd^{II} and Rh^{III} can be determined successfully with DPyT. The molar extinction coefficient and Sandell sensitivity values for the palladium complex are respectively $2.36 \times 10^4 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$, 0.0065 $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$ and those for rhodium $1.5 \times 10^4 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$, and 0.0065 $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$.

Several chromogenic reagents have been proposed for the spectrophotometric determination of Pd^{II} and Rh^{III}. In the present communication *N,N'*-dipyridylthiourea (DPyT) has been recommended as a sensitive as well as selective reagent for both Pd^{II} and Rh^{III}.

Results and Discussion

The absorbance spectra of complexes formed by palladium and rhodium with DPyT revealed λ_{\max} at 330 and 335 nm respectively, in chloroform extract. But all the measurements were taken at 340 nm for Pd and Rh where the reagent has minimum absorption. Pd and Rh DPyT complexes were found stable for 48 and 24 h respectively.

The maximum absorption of the palladium complex at different pH values are plotted and it is found that all the curves are similar and exhibit maximum absorption at 330 nm, indicating the formation of only one complex under the condition. Maximum and constant absorbance is exhibited in the pH range 4.4–5.6 for Pd-complex and 4.7–6.6 for Rh-complex.

The results of extraction coefficient and degrees of extraction of the palladium and rhodium complexes into various solvents show that chloroform ($3 \times 5 \text{ ml}$) extracts maximum 92.9% Pd-complex and 96.9% Rh-complex. The empirical formula of the complexes was determined by mole-ratio² method and verified by conventional slope-ratio method. The composition of the Pd-complex was found to be 2 : 1 (reagent : metal) and that for Rh-complex 3 : 1.

Ir study of the complexes : The solid complexes of palladium-DPyT and rhodium-DPyT were precipitated separately from acetate buffer medium, filtered, washed and dried. The ir spectra (KBr) of the complexes shows that the ligand bands at $1470\text{--}1435 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ (amide-II) shifted by $10\text{--}15 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ in the Pd-complex and by $15\text{--}20 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ in the Rh-complex, which suggests complexation through nitrogen. Again the band at $1350\text{--}1310 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ shifted to 1300 cm^{-1} in Pd-DPyT complex, whereas these bands

shifted by 10 cm^{-1} in the case of Rh-DPyT complex. These change also suggests the complexation through nitrogen. The bands at $1140, 1185 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ (C=S corresponding to amide-I)³ shifted and merged at 1150 cm^{-1} in both Pd and Rh complexes indicating complexation through sulphur atom of the ligand.

Effect of foreign ions : Experiments shows that it is possible to determine 72 μg of Pd^{II} and 89 μg of Rh^{III} reliably (within an error $\pm 2\%$) in presence of the following ions : Ti^{IV}, V^V, Cr^{III}, Ni^{II}, Cu^{II}, Cd^{II}, Sb^{III} (upto 1–2 mg) and Au^{III} (0.2 mg) in presence of EDTA²⁻ as masking agent. Mn^{IV}, Co^{III}, Pb^{II} (1–2 mg) in presence of tartarate, Zn^{II}, Bi^{III}, Mo^{VI}, W^{VI}, G^{VI} (1–2 mg) without any masking agent and Fe^{III} (1 mg), Hg^{II} (0.5 mg), Os^{VI} (5 mg) can be tolerated in presence of HF, KI, sulphurous acid reduction respectively. Pt^{IV} (0.5 mg) does not interfere if it is extracted first with chloroform in 0.5 N HCl medium after 15 min heating. Ir only interferes in the determination of Rh^{III} and Pd^{II} (upto 1 mg) and which must be extracted first at 4.5 pH in cold condition. Ir (upto 1 mg) do not interfere in case of Pd determination. Ru^{III} (0.2–0.3 mg) is tolerated if it is reduced with hydroxylamine hydrochloride at first.

Beer's law, molar absorptivity and sensitivity : Beer's law is obeyed over the range of 0.24–2.88 ppm of Pd and 0.6–3.56 ppm of Rh. The molar absorptivity and Sandells sensitivity are $2.36 \times 10^4 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$ and 0.004 $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$ for the Pd-complex and $1.5 \times 10^4 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$ and 0.0065 $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$ for the Rh-complex.

For 5 parallel determination of 1.92 ppm of Pd the relative mean error and standard deviations are 0.85% and 0.0162 respectively and those for 3.56 ppm of Rh are 0.97% and 0.041.

Determination of Pd and Rh in synthetic mixture : In order to confirm the usefulness, the proposed method was applied for the determination of Pd and Rh in various synthetic mixtures of platinum metals. Interference from base metals are negligible. So these are not repeated. The results are presented in Table 1.

TABLE I—DETERMINATION OF Pd AND Rh IN SYNTHETIC MIXTURES*

Sl. no.	Composition of mixture (in µg)	Metal ion found (µg)	Relative mean deviation (%)
1a.	Pd ^{II} (48.0), Rh ^{III} (120.0), Ru ^{III} (88.0), Os ^{VI} (100.0), Ir ^{III} (130.2), Pt ^{IV} (90.0)	Pd ^{II} (47.6)	0.33
2b.	Rh ^{III} (40), Pd ^{II} (96.0), Ru ^{III} (88.0), Os ^{VI} (100.0), Pt ^{IV} (90.0)	Rh ^{III} (39.0)	0.31
3c.	Pd ^{II} (48.0), Rh ^{III} (80.0)	Pd ^{II} (47.8),	0.21
		Rh ^{III} (79.2)	0.20

*Average of five determination. (a) Prior reduction of Pt^{IV}, Os^{VI} with sulphurous acid and Ru^{III} with hydroxylamine hydrochloride, Pd was extracted in cold, at requisite condition. (b) Following (a), Pd was extracted first then aqueous layer was treated for Rh^{III} and estimated. (c) Pd^{II} was extracted first then Rh^{III} extracted in hot condition from the aqueous layer and estimated.

N,N'-Dipyridylthiourea has been found to be a suitable reagent for the extraction and photometry of palladium and rhodium. The method is selective in the presence of commonly associated diverse ions especially in the presence of other platinum metals. Only iridium interferes in the determination rhodium. The sensitivity of the method for the determination of palladium and rhodium is comparable to that of recent selective procedures⁴.

Experimental

A Carl-Zeiss PMQ II spectrophotometer with 1 cm quartz cell was used. A Systronics pH meter equipped with glass and calomel electrodes was used for pH measurements.

Palladium chloride (PdCl₂) and rhodium chloride (RhCl₃ · 3H₂O) J.M. were dissolved separately in dilute HCl and standardised⁵. Standard solutions of the other metals were prepared by dissolving their salts in distilled water or dilute HCl. Hydrochloric acid and 10% sodium

acetate solution were employed for regulation of acidity of the solutions. All the chemicals used were of AnalaR grade.

Preparation of organic reagent : DPyT was synthesised by heating a mixture of 2-aminopyridine (0.2 mol) in ethanol, CS₂ (0.1 mol) following standard method⁶ and a little powdered KOH on a water-bath for 8 h. Excess CS₂ was then distilled off and the resulting solid was crystallised from rectified spirit as needle shaped shining white crystals, m.p. 146°. Its elemental analysis (C, 57.68; N, 24.04; H, 4.40; S, 13.92%) was in agreement with the formula C₁₁H₁₀N₄S. A 1 × 10⁻² M solution of the reagent in spec. -pure alcohol was used.

Procedure : An aliquot containing known amount of Pd^{II} was taken, its pH adjusted to 4.4–5.6 with dilute HCl and Na-acetate solution, then the reagent solution (1–2 ml) was then added and the mixture was allowed to stand for 5 min. The yellow coloured complex produced instantly was extracted with chloroform (3 × 5 ml), made up to 25 ml with chloroform, then dried and its absorbance was measured at 340 nm against reagent blank.

In the case of Rh^{III}, the pH was adjusted to 4.7–6.6 with HCl and 10% sodium acetate solution. After addition of the reagent solution the mixture was heated over a boiling water-bath for 30–35 min and cooled to room temperature. Subsequent extraction and absorbance measurements at 340 nm were the same as for Pd^{II}.

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